

1 **Direct Chemical Lithography Writing on 2D Materials by Electron Beam Induced Chemical**
2 **Reactions**

3
4 *Iryna Danylo, Lukáš Koláčný, Kristína Kissíková, Tomáš Hartman, Martina Pitínová, Jiří Šturala,*
5 *Zdeněk Sofer*, Martin Veselý**

6
7 I. Danylo, L. Koláčný, K. Kissíková, M. Pitínová, M. Veselý
8 Department of Organic Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague 166 28,
9 Czech Republic
10 E-mail: veselyr@vscht.cz

11
12 T. Hartman, J. Šturala, Z. Sofer
13 Department of Inorganic Chemistry, University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague 166 28,
14 Czech Republic
15 E-mail: soferz@vscht.cz

16
17 **Keywords:** 2D materials, platinum nanoparticles, direct electron beam lithography, target-
18 controlled depositions, nanoparticle-support interactions

19
20 Due to their high surface-to-volume ratio, two-dimensional (2D) materials are used as supports
21 for metal nanoparticle catalysts. Various methods exist to prepare such materials, but controlling
22 the size and distribution of the deposited nanoparticles (NPs) remains a challenge. Here, the use of
23 electron beam lithography is investigated for the target and controlled deposition of metal
24 nanoparticles. A dual-beam focused ion beam-scanning electron microscope is used to direct the
25 deposition of platinum nanoparticles onto 2D functionalized graphene oxide and black phosphorus
26 sheets. The deposition is conducted at various exposure times and particle distribution. SEM shows
27 the amount and distribution of the supported nanoparticles, TEM confirms their size. Raman
28 spectroscopy reveals a strong bonding between the nanoparticles and the support sheets according
29 to the type of 2D support. Thus, electron beam lithography is a promising method for the target-
30 controlled deposition of nanoparticles onto 2D materials, which enables evaluating the specific
31 influence of the nanoparticle-support interaction on enhanced catalytic activity.

32 1. Introduction

33 Two-dimensional (2D) materials have attracted significant attention owing to their unique
34 morphology, large surface area, and excellent optical and electrical properties. As a typical 2D
35 material, graphene has been widely investigated for catalysis.^[1-3] Due to the perturbations in its
36 perfect hexagonal structure, graphene can be modified to promote its catalytic properties. Recently,
37 other 2D material families, such as black phosphorus,^[4, 5] transition metal dichalcogenides
38 (TMDs),^[6] and transition metal carbides and nitrides (MXenes),^[7] have been studied in the fields
39 of photocatalysis, electrocatalysis, and thermocatalysis. Moreover, 2D materials are promising
40 supports for metal nanoparticle-based catalysts.

41 Various studies have shown that 2D material-supported metal catalysts exhibit significantly
42 improved catalytic performance. For instance, Wang *et al.* ^[8] reported a 2D tungsten oxide (WO₃)
43 supported catalyst with enhanced activity for CO oxidation. The 2D WO₃ nanosheets increased the
44 stability of noble metals and improved the metal-support interaction, leading to a higher specific
45 surface area and increased catalytic activity. Later, Lin *et al.* ^[4] suggested a novel 2D material,
46 black phosphorus (BP), as a support for the construction of a Ni₂P-based hybrid catalyst. This
47 catalyst exhibited high catalytic activity, conductivity, and good stability for the hydrogen
48 evolution reaction, all of which were attributed to the strong interaction between the Ni₂P NPs and
49 BP. Thus, the enhanced catalytic performance of 2D material-supported metal catalysts appears to
50 be due to the electronic properties of the 2D support and to the interaction between the metal
51 nanoparticles (NPs) and support.^[9-11] However, the metal-support interaction is difficult to
52 precisely qualify and quantify. To achieve this, the individual contribution of the NPs and support
53 must be evaluated, and the only way of ensuring this request is to deposit identical patterns of
54 supported NPs of defined size and spatial distribution on various 2D supports differing in physical,
55 chemical, and electronic properties.

56 Several methods exist for the preparation of 2D material-supported metal nanoparticle catalysts,
57 but each has drawbacks. Traditionally, impregnation has been the most common technique due to
58 its simplicity. In this technique, a loading solution containing metal precursors is mixed with the
59 support and then the solvent is evaporated. Slot *et al.* ^[12] used this procedure to prepare platinum
60 (Pt) NPs on MXenes as supports. Although the morphology of the prepared catalysts presented
61 uniformly distributed metal particles, there were major differences in the particle size distribution.
62 Another traditional method is co-precipitation, by which a solution of an active metal and a support
63 are mixed, supersaturated, and grown as a combined solid precursor. This method was used by

64 Ahmed *et al.* ^[13] for the synthesis of two efficient catalysts based on CuAl- and CoAl-layered
65 double hydroxides (LDH) supported on graphene oxide. The synthesized catalysts demonstrated
66 well-exfoliated graphene oxide (GO) sheets, completely covered by LDH particles. The
67 morphological investigations of the LDH particles showed the lateral particle size of several
68 hundred nanometers for CuAl-LDH and up to 8 μm for CoAL-LDH. Scanning electron microscopy
69 (SEM) indicated clustering of the individual LDH particles into larger aggregates, while
70 transmission electron microscopy (TEM) confirmed their hexagonal and platelet-like shape. At the
71 same time, the packing of the individual LDH particles within the CoAl-LDH/GO sample appeared
72 relatively random. Another method is hydrothermal synthesis, a solution reaction-based approach
73 under high temperature and high-pressure water conditions. It involves crystal synthesis from
74 substances that are insoluble at ordinary temperatures and pressures. Gao *et al.* ^[14] used this
75 approach to prepare noble metal NPs on a 2D Bi_2WO_6 nanosheet support. Although the
76 morphology and structure of the material showed well-dispersed NPs on the surface of the Bi_2WO_6
77 nanosheets, the size distribution histogram of the metal NPs indicated a variation of particle size
78 in the range from 3 to 8 nm and inhomogeneity. More recently, atomic layer deposition (ALD) has
79 been developed as an effective method for the synthesis of supported catalysts. ALD is a gas-phase
80 method based on a unique reaction mechanism, known as the self-limited surface saturation
81 reaction. Mostly, two self-limited surface reactions occur and deposit a binary compound film,
82 which leads to the deposition of a thin film with atomic level control.^[15] For this, gaseous reactants
83 (precursors) are introduced into the reaction chamber to form the desired material via chemical
84 surface reactions. This method was used by Lee *et al.* ^[16] to deposit Pt NPs on 2D molybdenum
85 disulfide (MoS_2). The surface of the catalysts with Pt NPs exhibited an enhanced coverage with a
86 quite homogeneous particle growth and the root-mean-square roughness of NPs was 1.15 ± 0.10 ,
87 0.95 ± 0.09 and 0.80 ± 0.12 nm at 10, 20, and 50 ALD cycles. Despite this, for the deposition of
88 small and evenly distributed NPs, ALD requires activation of the MoS_2 surface by plasma
89 pretreatment. Mackus *et al.* ^[17] combined ALD with electron beam-induced deposition (EBID) for
90 the fabrication of Pt nanostructures. This technique included the preparation of a thin layer using
91 EBID and the selective thickening of the prepared layer using ALD. The main advantage of this
92 technique was the deposition of a high Pt content by treating the EBID layer to O_2 before the ALD
93 step. This improvement allowed the purification of the Pt NPs deposited by EBID and reduced the
94 required electron dose to enhance the technique throughput. Although the throughput of the

95 technique was improved, the overall preparation time consisted of two steps, and a pre-treated stage
96 potentially reduces the competitiveness of this technique.

97 The above-described methods and studies show that controlling the particle density, size, and
98 distribution of deposited NPs remains an unsolved challenge. However, electron beam lithography
99 (EBL) could be ideal for the controlled fabrication of supported metal NPs on 2D sheet surface.
100 The main advantage of EBL is that it is able to perform direct and targeted deposition on a desired
101 2D sheet of NPs independent of the local topography. This makes it possible to choose a sheet with
102 specific characteristics, such as shape, chemical composition, and electronic properties, and leads
103 to accessibility of deposited NPs for all characterization techniques. Moreover, EBL is a highly
104 powerful tool that can prepare features with a precision of 10 nm ^[18-20] at the desired spot of the
105 material. These features are extremely useful for correlative spectro-microscopy, because they are
106 big enough to be spatially distinguishable in determining a time-resolved microcatalytic activity
107 using single-molecule fluorescence microscopy. Thus, EBL can be used to prepare an identical
108 pattern of NPs on different 2D materials to investigate and evaluate the specific effect of the 2D
109 support.

110 In this study, we present the first use of direct EBL incorporated in a dual-beam focused ion beam-
111 scanning electron microscope (FIB-SEM) equipped with a gas injection system (GIS) to fabricate
112 Pt NPs on 2D materials directly from a Pt organometallic precursor. We demonstrate the technique
113 on the 2D materials: black phosphorus (BP) and graphene oxide, functionalized with epoxy and
114 hydroxyl (HUGO) or carboxyl (TOGO) groups. The nanofabricated Pt NPs on 2D materials allow
115 the specific interaction between the metal NPs and support to be comprehensively studied using
116 model systems with different electronic properties of the support. The characterization of these
117 systems allows us to evaluate the exclusive influence of the support on the intensity of the
118 interaction between the active site on the prepared materials.

119

120 **2. Results and discussion**

121 **2.1 Characterization of 2D support materials**

122 The high-pressure conversion,^[21] Hummers ^[22] and Tour ^[23] methods were used to prepare the
123 following 2D materials for the controlled deposition of Pt NPs: black phosphorus (BP); graphene
124 oxide functionalized with epoxy and hydroxyl groups (HUGO); and graphene oxide functionalized
125 with carboxyl groups (TOGO) (see Experimental Section). The prepared materials were
126 characterized by a range of microscopic and spectroscopic techniques.

127 SEM revealed the morphology of the prepared 2D support materials, most of which had smooth
 128 flat surfaces that represented their layered structure (**Figure 1a, d, 2a, d, 3a, d**). The lateral size of
 129 the 2D sheets predominantly ranged from 5 to 30 μm for both GO materials and from 10 to 50 μm
 130 for BP. Furthermore, the energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) maps (Figure 1b, 2b, 3b)
 131 and spectra (Figure 1c, 2c, 3c) indicated the presence of oxygen and carbon in the GO sheets, as
 132 well as the presence of phosphorus in the BP sheets. The presence of the contaminant sulfur was
 133 also observed in TOGO and HUGO (2.65 and 0.52 wt.%, respectively), differing according to the
 134 preparation method (**Table 1**). In the case of the BP sheets, the presence of adventitious carbon and
 135 oxygen originates from the surface adsorption and surface oxidation of BP.^[21] Nevertheless, both
 136 SEM and EDS verified the formation of GO and BP 2D sheets.

137 **Table 1.** Elemental composition of 2D support materials

Element	Apparent Concentration			k Ratio			Weight [%]		
	TOGO	HUGO	BP	TOGO	HUGO	BP	TOGO	HUGO	BP
C	86.89	138.70	0.00	0.86893	1.38697	0.00002	56.22	65.84	5.76
O	76.08	68.76	0.00	0.25602	0.23139	0.00000	41.13	33.64	0.25
S	9.10	1.56	-	0.07839	0.01342	-	2.65	0.52	-
P	-	-	0.71	-	-	0.00399	-	-	93.99

138

139
 140 **Figure 1.** TOGO support material: a) SEM image; b) EDS mapping of elements obtained from
 141 SEM in (a): red – carbon, green – oxygen, blue – sulfur; c) EDS spectrum; d) magnified SEM
 142 image with detailed focus on single sheets

143
 144 **Figure 2.** HUGO support material: a) SEM image; b) EDS mapping of elements obtained from
 145 SEM in (a): red – carbon, green – oxygen, blue – sulfur; c) EDS spectrum; d) magnified SEM
 146 image with detailed focus on single sheets

147
 148 **Figure 3.** BP support material: a) SEM image; b) EDS mapping of elements obtained from SEM
 149 in (a): red – carbon, green – oxygen, purple – phosphorus; c) EDS spectrum; d) magnified SEM
 150 image with detailed focus on single sheets

151
 152 TEM confirmed the morphological properties of the 2D support materials and provided more
 153 detailed information regarding their crystal structure (**Figure 4**). The low-resolution TEM (LR-
 154 TEM) of TOGO (Figure 4a) showed twisted sheets entangled with each other, while the LR-TEM
 155 of HUGO and BP (Figure 4c, 4e) exhibited few-layered nanosheets highly transparent for
 156 electrons. Simultaneously, the high-resolution TEM (HR-TEM) of both GO types (Figure 4b, 4d)
 157 revealed graphite lattices with ordered and disordered regions. This means that the graphene

158 nanosheets were partly recovered to an ordered crystal structure. In addition, selected-area electron
159 diffraction confirmed the 6-fold pattern (inset in Figure 4b, 4d) of the diffraction spots for the GO
160 materials, thereby indicating a crystalline order related to a hexagonal lattice. At the same time, the
161 BP electron diffraction pattern disclosed a hexagonal lattice spacing of 0.26 nm from the BP plane
162 [400] (Figure 4f).

163

164

165 **Figure 4.** LR-TEM images: a) TOGO sheet; c) HUGO sheet; e) BP sheet. HR-TEM images and
166 electron diffraction: b) TOGO sheet; d) HUGO sheet; f) BP sheet

167

168 Raman spectroscopy identified the chemical properties of the prepared 2D sheets by determining
169 the main vibration modes of the GO and BP materials (**Figure 5**). For HUGO and TOGO, the first
170 peak, the G band, occurred at 1598 cm^{-1} and 1594 cm^{-1} , respectively (Figure 5a). Because this peak
171 is usually observed at 1585 cm^{-1} ,^[24] this indicates a G band blue shift. The most plausible
172 explanation for this blue shift is that an isolated C–C bond resonates at frequencies higher than the
173 G band of graphite.^[25] The second peak, the D band, appeared at 1340 cm^{-1} and 1344 cm^{-1} for
174 HUGO and TOGO, respectively (Figure 5a); this is within the typical range of 1250 cm^{-1} to
175 1400 cm^{-1} .^[26] Normalized intensity (I_D/I_G ratio), used to quantify structural defects,^[27] was 1.35
176 and 2.03 for HUGO and TOGO, respectively (**Table 2 and 3**). The higher I_D/I_G ratio for TOGO is

177 consistent with a broad and strong D peak indicating lattice distortions and a large number of sp^3 -
 178 like defects. This higher number of defects may be associated with the extensive oxidation of
 179 graphite and the destruction of its periodic structure during the functionalization of TOGO by
 180 carboxyl groups. In the case of BP, the three prominent peaks related to the A_g^1 , B_{2g} and A_g^2 phonon
 181 modes occurred at 360, 433 and 460 cm^{-1} , respectively (Figure 5b). The presence of all main
 182 phonon modes in the Raman spectrum indicated the crystalline structure of the BP nanosheets after
 183 exfoliation.^[28]

184
 185 **Figure 5.** Raman spectra: a) HUGO and TOGO; b) BP

186
 187 **Table 2.** Raman data for deposited Pt NPs on TOGO

Sample	Deposition time [s]	FWHM of G peak	FWHM of D peak	I_D/I_G	L_a [nm]
1	0	101.23	123.78	2.03	9.47
2	0.03	73.60	129.63	2.75	7.00
3	0.06	66.04	127.59	4.21	4.57
4	0.09	84.85	138.58	2.10	9.14
5	0.12	91.74	136.14	1.90	10.11
6	0.15	95.27	101.70	1.60	12.05
7	0.21	97.73	114.85	1.32	14.54
8	0.30	76.22	132.15	2.52	7.63
9	0.70	65.52	120.55	3.66	5.25
10	1.00	88.99	122.47	1.66	11.57

189 **Table 3.** Raman data for deposited Pt NPs on HUGO

Sample	Deposition time [s]	FWHM of G peak	FWHM of D peak	I_D/I_G	L_a [nm]
1	0	107.83	119.71	1.35	14.20
2	0.03	92.78	96.35	1.80	10.69
3	0.06	84.41	99.92	2.09	9.19
4	0.09	91.43	118.01	1.62	11.85
5	0.12	89.51	103.88	2.47	7.79
6	0.15	79.51	95.66	2.13	9.02
7	0.18	82.46	111.52	3.27	5.88
8	0.21	91.93	100.19	1.44	13.34
9	0.70	80.31	92.91	1.49	12.89

190

191 Overall, these techniques show that the prepared 2D materials not only exhibit excellent
 192 morphology in the form of few-layered nanosheets but also possess the required chemical
 193 composition and structure. Collectively, these attributes enable their use as supports for the targeted
 194 deposition of Pt NPs by EBL.

195

196 **2.2 Characterization of Pt NPs deposited onto 2D support materials**

197

198 *2.2.1 Morphological properties and chemical composition*

199 SEM showed that the morphological structure of the Pt NPs directly deposited on the 2D supports
 200 by EBL exhibited a regular square lattice pattern in all cases (insets in **Figure 6a-c**). Moreover, the
 201 insets exhibit that uniformly sized Pt NPs were deposited on targeted areas of the support in precise
 202 amounts and with the required spatial distribution. The size of Pt NPs increased as the exposure
 203 (deposition) time enlarged (Figure 6a-c), ranging from 23 ± 2 , 23 ± 2 and 25 ± 1.2 nm to 68 ± 4 ,
 204 68 ± 3 and 75 ± 2 nm for BP, TOGO and HUGO sheets, respectively. Interestingly, over the entire
 205 exposure time, the Pt NPs deposited on the HUGO sheets were always larger than those deposited
 206 on the BP and TOGO sheets, which were consistently around the same size. This phenomenon
 207 could be explained by the high chemical reactivity of BP and TOGO, which serves as a reductant
 208 in the deposition of Pt NPs.^[29] Consequently, the deposited NPs may be characterized by a higher

209 Pt content due to the reduced number of impurities from the Pt organometallic precursor. Although
210 SEM instrumental magnification was utilized to define the NP morphology, high-resolution TEM
211 analysis was required to precisely estimate and confirm the distribution of the smaller NPs.

212
213 **Figure 6.** Dependence of Pt NP size from deposition time: a) Pt/TOGO; b) Pt/HUGO; c) Pt/BP.
214 Calculated values of confidence interval for each deposition time from statistical analysis of
215 minimum 25 NPs

216
217 TEM verified that the supported Pt NPs were successfully deposited in an identical uniformly sized
218 pattern. More importantly, and contrary to what SEM appeared to present, it revealed that the
219 deposited Pt NPs were not individual particles but, in fact, the clusters of much smaller particles
220 (insets in **Figure 7, 8, and 9**). The Pt/HUGO NPs exhibited the largest average size of 1.4 ± 0.3 nm,
221 while the Pt/TOGO and Pt/BP NPs had similar size ranges of 1.3 ± 0.3 and 1.3 ± 0.2 nm,
222 respectively (the pixel size of TEM images was 0.02 nm). Furthermore, the HR-TEM images
223 shown in the insets in Figure 7, 8, 9 and S1 demonstrate the formation of finely dispersed Pt NPs.
224 Additionally, these HR-TEM images were used for FFT pattern calculations, in which diffraction
225 spots attributed to the Pt [110] plane with interplanar distances of 0.28 nm (insets in Figure 7b, 8b,
226 9b, and Figure 7c, 8c, 9c, S1). As reported by Lin *et al.*,^[4] the high dispersion of metal NPs on 2D
227 BP is probably due to the strong synergistic combination of NPs and BP. In the case of GO

228 supports, several researchers have suggested that oxygenated functional groups act as anchor sites
229 for Pt complexes supported on graphene oxide.^[30] Furthermore, these groups also play the main
230 role in stabilizing the NP-support interface, which prevents NP sintering.^[30] Thus, the existence of
231 smaller unsintered individual particles with good dispersion implies that more active sites can be
232 displayed to increase catalytic activity.

233
234 **Figure 7.** TEM and HR-TEM images of deposited Pt NPs on TOGO sheets for deposition time:
235 a) 0.3 s; b) 1.0 s; c) FFT pattern calculated from HR-TEM image in Figure S1; d) EDS elemental
236 map of platinum

237
238 **Figure 8.** TEM and HR-TEM images of deposited Pt NPs on HUGO sheets for deposition time:
239 a) 0.3 s; b) 1.0 s; c) FFT pattern calculated from HR-TEM image in b; d) EDS elemental map of
240 platinum

241

242

243 **Figure 9.** TEM and HR-TEM images of deposited Pt NPs on BP sheets for deposition time:
244 a) 0.3 s; b) 1.0 s; c) FFT pattern calculated from HR-TEM image in b; d) EDS elemental map
245 platinum

246

247 Additionally, EDS indicated the presence of Pt (Figure 7d, 8d, 9d), as well as of O, C and P
248 elements (Figure S2) in the Pt/GO and Pt/BP materials. However, an increase in C and O can also
249 be observed in the area related to the deposited NPs. The most likely sources of increased C and O
250 are the precursor molecules themselves or contamination from the SEM chamber and/or GIS
251 needle.^[31, 32] Despite this, the Pt profile recorded throughout the materials (Figure S3) clearly
252 confirmed the formation of Pt in the prepared samples.

253

254 2.2.2 Structural properties

255 The structural properties of a catalyst influence the reactivity of active sites and, consequently, can
256 enhance the catalytic performance. Raman spectroscopy revealed strong bonding between the Pt
257 NPs and the support sheets, but different behavior according to the type of 2D support. For Pt NPs
258 deposited on GO supports, regardless of the deposition time, the Raman spectra exhibited G and D
259 vibration modes centered at $1585\text{--}1599\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1336\text{--}1348\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively (Figure S4a, c).
260 More importantly, the spectrum of pristine HUGO had a lower intensity than its post-deposition
261 spectra, while pristine TOGO had a higher intensity, with its strong and broad D peak indicating
262 lattice distortions and high defect density. To quantify post-deposition defects, the full width at
263 half maximum (FWHM) values of the D and G peaks were calculated by using a Gaussian fit for

264 the Raman spectroscopy data and plotted as the I_D/I_G ratio (Figure S4b, d). These ratios for
 265 Pt/HUGO increased as the deposition time increased, while for Pt/TOGO the ratios first increased
 266 and then decreased. The I_D/I_G ratios ranged from 1.32-2.75 to 1.44-3.27 for Pt/TOGO and
 267 Pt/HUGO, respectively (Tables 2, 3), but a few highly defective points were detected
 268 corresponding to values up to 4.21. Furthermore, a 2D contour plot of the D/G band ratio
 269 (**Figure 10d, 11d**) constructed from Raman maps exposed that changes in the ratio were related to
 270 the area covered by Pt NPs. In the figures, the optical images of Pt NPs deposited on TOGO
 271 (Figure 10a) and HUGO (Figure 11a) show the region of 2D sheets for measurements (green
 272 outline), while the SEM insets (Figure 10b, 11b) demonstrate the precise spot of Pt NPs studied
 273 via Raman mapping owing to correlative microscopy approach. The 2D contour plots of the D/G
 274 band ratio and D band intensity (Figure 10d, e, 11d, e) provided information about the uniform
 275 spatial distribution of the main peak intensities within the explored region, but the area covered by
 276 Pt NPs was characterized by the lower values, which is in good agreement with the decreased
 277 intensities of the D and G bands. The changes in the D/G band ratio can be attributed to the recovery
 278 of sp^2 -hybridized domains induced by Pt deposition.^[33]
 279

280
 281 **Figure 10.** Raman characterization of deposited Pt NPs on TOGO sheet: a) Optical image of TOGO
 282 sheet with highlighted area of interest by green outline; b) SEM image of deposited Pt NP precise
 283 spot studied via Raman mapping due to correlative approach; c) Raman spectrum. Raman 2D
 284 contour plot of same spot from optical image highlighted by black rectangle: d) D/G band ratio; e)
 285 D band
 286

287
 288 **Figure 11.** Raman characterization of deposited Pt NPs on HUGO sheet: a) Optical image of
 289 HUGO sheet with highlighted area of interest by green outline; b) SEM image of deposited Pt NP
 290 precise spot studied via Raman mapping due to correlative approach; c) Raman spectrum. Raman
 291 2D contour plot of same spot from optical image highlighted by black rectangle: d) D/G band ratio;
 292 e) D band

293
 294 Thus, Pt NP deposition on the GO supports with the lowest exposure time led to a rise in the D-
 295 band intensity due to the introduction of structural defects. While the perfect structure of graphene
 296 prevailed over such defects, the intensity of the D band increased. A longer exposure time led to
 297 the amorphization of the crystalline structure and reduction of both Raman peaks.

298 The spectra of Pt NPs deposited on BP exhibited three main peaks (A_g^1 , B_{2g} , A_g^2) for all deposition
 299 times (Figure S5), but the general behavior of the spectra was the opposite of that observed for the
 300 Pt/GO materials; in other words, the intensity of the main peaks increased as the deposition time
 301 increased. The only exception to this was observed for A_g^1 at the deposition time of 0.27 s.
 302 However, the spectrum of pristine BP had the highest intensity of all peaks, which made the
 303 properties of pristine BP closer to the properties of pristine TOGO. Furthermore, the Pt/BP spectra
 304 exposed a significant Raman shift not only for the B_{2g} and A_g^2 in-plane modes, but also for the A_g^1
 305 out-of-plane mode in the ranges of 459–465, 432–437, and 358–362 cm^{-1} , respectively. According
 306 to the literature,^[34] Raman shifts of the B_{2g} and A_g^2 intraplane modes are dependent on the thickness
 307 of the sheet, but the A_g^1 interplane mode remains unchanged. In the case of Pt/BP, this A_g^1
 308 phenomenon could be attributed to the presence of Pt NPs, similar to the anomalous behavior of
 309 E_{2g}^1 in MoS_2 due to the presence of molybdenum atoms.^[35, 36] Furthermore, the intensity ratios of

310 A_g^1 and A_g^2 modes (**Table 4**) confirmed the decreased values within the area covered by Pt NPs
 311 (**Figure 12d, e**), thereby confirming the influence of Pt deposition on the BP structure.

312

313
 314 **Figure 12.** Raman characterization of deposited Pt NPs on BP: a) SEM image of BP sheet with
 315 highlighted area of interest by green rectangle; b) SEM image of Pt NP precise spot studied via
 316 Raman mapping due to correlative approach; c) Raman spectrum. Raman 2D contour plot of same
 317 spot from SEM image highlighted by green rectangle: d) A_g^1 band ratio; e) A_g^2 band ratio

318

319 Simultaneously, Raman analysis was used to identify the in-plane crystallite size (L_a) of the
 320 Pt/TOGO and Pt/HUGO materials, which was calculated by the following equation:^[37]

321

$$322 \quad L_a = 2.4 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot \lambda^4 \cdot \left(\frac{I_D}{I_G}\right)^{-1} \quad (1)$$

323

324 where λ is the wavelength of the excitation laser (532 nm) used in the Raman measurements.

325 The calculated crystallite size trend revealed that the average domain sizes of Pt/TOGO and
 326 Pt/HUGO do not depend on Pt deposition. For the former, the average crystallite size first
 327 decreased and then increased, while for the latter, the size decreased. For pristine TOGO and
 328 HUGO, L_a was 9.47 and 14.20, respectively. For the Pt/TOGO and Pt/HUGO NPs, the L_a
 329 distribution ranged from 4.57 to 14.54 (Table 2) and from 5.88 to 13.34 (Table 3), respectively.
 330 Such variations in size values can be attributed to a susceptibility of TOGO and HUGO to a high-
 331 temperature exfoliation and affected by the number of GO layers.^[38]

332 **Table 4.** Raman data for deposited Pt NPs on BP

Sample	Deposition time [s]	FWHM of A ¹ _g	FWHM of B _{2g}	FWHM of A ² _g	A ¹ _g band ratio	B _{2g} band ratio	A ² _g band ratio
1	0	5.8361	8.1173	6.8066	0.0026	0.0036	0.0031
2	0.03	6.2332	10.0110	7.0276	0.0040	0.0064	0.0045
3	0.06	4.8002	5.6405	4.9276	0.0404	0.0475	0.0415
4	0.09	5.1594	6.2552	5.2171	0.0449	0.0544	0.0454
5	0.12	5.5340	7.8796	6.5187	0.0040	0.0057	0.0048
6	0.15	5.3442	6.6826	5.8866	0.0098	0.0123	0.0108
7	0.18	4.8088	5.6275	4.9844	0.0006	0.0007	0.0006
8	0.21	5.0124	6.0918	5.2188	0.0007	0.0009	0.0008
9	0.24	6.3771	9.2567	7.0803	0.0059	0.0085	0.0065
10	0.27	8.7104	11.9012	7.7900	0.0017	0.0023	0.0015
11	0.30	5.9336	8.3555	6.3300	0.0086	0.0121	0.0092
9	0.70	5.9944	8.7880	7.0131	0.0044	0.0064	0.0051
10	1.00	5.8266	8.4204	6.7112	0.0022	0.0032	0.0025

333
334 Overall, Raman analysis revealed that Pt deposition caused structural changes in graphene oxide
335 and black phosphorus, which were proven not only by the decrease in I_D/I_G ratio values and the
336 increase in the A¹_g and A²_g intensity ratios but also by a substantial Raman shift for all modes in
337 the Pt/BP spectra. These structural changes were driven by the dependence of Pt NP size on the
338 deposition time, thereby enabling the controlled deposition of identical NP patterns, with fixed
339 density and spatial distribution, using electron beam lithography. Thus, varying the deposition time
340 and 2D support makes it possible to control the structural properties of a prepared material to
341 enhance its catalytic activity.

342 343 **3. Conclusions**

344 To our best knowledge, we are the first to report the utilization of direct electron beam lithography,
345 incorporated in a dual-beam FIB-SEM microscope equipped with a gas injection system, to
346 fabricate Pt NPs on 2D support materials with the controllable density, size, and distribution. This
347 method allowed us to prepare an identical pattern of Pt NPs on three 2D supports (BP, HUGO, and

348 TOGO) to evaluate the specific influence of the NP-support interaction on enhanced catalytic
349 activity. SEM confirmed a regular square lattice pattern in all cases and showed that Pt NPs
350 increased as the deposition time enlarged. Simultaneously, TEM revealed that Pt NPs were the
351 clusters of smaller individual particles. The Pt/HUGO NPs had the largest average size of $1.4 \pm$
352 0.3 nm, while the Pt/TOGO and Pt/BP NPs had a similar size of 1.3 ± 0.3 and 1.3 ± 0.2 nm,
353 respectively. Furthermore, the HR-TEM images demonstrated the formation of finely dispersed Pt
354 NPs on the surface of 2D supports, which can be assumed to the strong synergistic effect between
355 NPs and 2D material due to a high chemical reactivity of the latter. Moreover, oxygenated
356 functional groups on the GO surface played the major role in stabilizing the NP-support interface,
357 which led to the prevention of NP sintering and indicated that more active sites can be disclosed to
358 enhance catalytic activity. Raman measurements exposed that Pt deposition changed the nature of
359 black phosphorus and graphene oxide based on the dependence of Pt NP size on the deposition
360 time. These changes were confirmed by the intensity ratios of the increase in the A^1_g and A^2_g , as
361 well as the decrease in I_D/I_G ratio values. Therefore, varying only the 2D support materials with
362 different electronic properties and the deposition time provides an opportunity to control the
363 structural properties of a prepared material to increase its catalytic activity. It also seems that the
364 optimized parameters of the NP microstructure, such as particle size and spatial distribution, could
365 be applicable for other preparation methods. Thus, the obtained Pt NPs on 2D support material
366 enable a particular investigation of the specific interaction between the metal NPs and the support.

367

368 4. Experimental Section

369

370 *Preparation of BP, HUGO, and TOGO sheets.* BP was obtained by high-pressure conversion of
371 red phosphorus with the following procedure:^[21] red phosphorus powder (10 g, 99.999%) was
372 compressed into a pellet (20 mm in diameter), covered with a graphite foil, and placed in a uniaxial
373 belt-type anvil cell. The conversion conditions were as follows: the pressure of 6 GPa at 600 °C,
374 the heating and cooling rates/min with a dwell on 600 °C for 30 minutes. After this, the compressed
375 BP pellet was mechanically separated from the graphite paper, grounded, and exfoliated using
376 shear force milling (Ultra-Turax T18 milling device) in acetonitrile under an argon atmosphere.
377 The exfoliation was carried out for 1 hour at a milling speed of 10000 rpm.

378 HUGO was prepared by the commonly used Hummers method.^[22] Graphite powder (5.0 g) and
379 sodium nitrate (2.5 g) were added to cooled concentrated sulfuric acid (115 mL) at 0 °C and stirred

380 for about 30 minutes to form a uniform mixture. The mixture was kept in an ice bath allowing the
381 temperature not to rise above 20 °C. Then potassium permanganate (15 g) was added gradually to
382 the above mixture with stirring and cooling. After removing the ice bath, the mixture was stirred
383 and heated up to 35 °C for 30 minutes to thicken the reaction mixture into the paste. As soon as the
384 thick paste was observed, deionized (DI) water (250 mL) was slowly added, and the obtained
385 mixture was heated to 70 °C and was held at a constant temperature for 15 minutes. After that, the
386 reaction was terminated by the addition of a large amount of DI water (1 L) and 3% of
387 H₂O₂ solution, which was confirmed by a mixture color-changing from black to bright yellow. The
388 obtained material was washed in DI water to remove the metal ions by repeated centrifugation. The
389 washing procedure was repeated until a negative reaction on sulfate ions was reached. The dried
390 GO was achieved by drying at 60 °C for 48 hours.

391 TOGO sheets were synthesized by Tour method.^[23] The solution of concentrated sulfuric and
392 phosphoric acids (360 and 40 mL, respectively) was added to the mixture of graphite powder
393 (3.0 g) and potassium permanganate (18.0 g). The reaction mixture was heated to 50 °C and stirred
394 for 12 h. After cooling, the mixture was poured into a flask with ice (400 mL) and hydrogen
395 peroxide (3 mL). The reaction mixture was filtered, and the filtrate obtained was centrifuged to
396 decant the supernatant. Afterward, the remaining solid material was purified by multiple washing
397 process in succession with deionized water, hydrochloric acid, and ethanol followed by repeated
398 centrifugation. Finally, the obtained GO was vacuum-dried overnight at room temperature.

399
400 *Platinum deposition by EBL.* For platinum deposition on a 2D support, direct EBL incorporated
401 into a dual-beam FIB-SEM microscope (Lyra3 GMU Tescan, Czech Republic) equipped with a
402 GIS (Ga⁺ LMIS) was used. Due to a GIS, the reacting molecules of a Pt organometallic precursor
403 (OP) were introduced as a gas in the working area and modified charged particle interactions with
404 a 2D support surface. While the Pt OP gas was adsorbed on the surface of a 2D support due to van
405 der Waals forces, the energy brought by the electron beam dissociated these molecules and formed
406 the bonds between the Pt NPs and a 2D support. Pt deposition was performed using precise working
407 parameters for both the injected gas (injection pressure 1.5×10^{-4} Pa, nozzle temperature 90 °C)
408 and the focused electron beam (beam current 170 pA, high voltage 30.0 kV, spot size 3.6 nm).
409 During deposition, the distance between a GIS and the 2D support surface was below 1 mm.
410 According to Pt NP size, the deposition was conducted for various deposition times ranging from
411 0.03 to 1.0 s (step 0.03 s) and several types of particle distributions (100–300 nm). For the purpose

412 of confocal Raman microscopy with an optical resolution limit of ~ 200 nm, we decided to use the
413 spatial distance between the NPs larger than this limit, although EBL itself allows unambiguously
414 distinguish NPs in the distance of 20-30 nm (see SI, Figure S6). It was necessary to deposit Pt NPs
415 with a specific size, spatial distribution, and distance larger than the resolution of confocal
416 microscopy (~ 200 nm) to exclude the influence of the interaction between the active sites of the
417 supports. For this reason, the deposition followed a regular square lattice pattern as the most
418 beneficial structure-oriented form, which can be easily reproducible on various supports. A
419 schematic illustration of the Pt deposition onto a 2D support by EBL is shown in **Figure 13**.
420

421
422 **Figure 13.** Illustration of Pt deposition onto 2D support by EBL

423
424 *Material characterizations.* SEM was used to indicate the amount and spatial distribution of the
425 supported NPs onto a 2D material. The measurements were performed on the Tescan Lyra3 dual-
426 beam microscope with a field emission gun (FEG) electron source (Tescan, Czech Republic) using
427 an accelerating voltage of 10 kV. EDS maps and spectra were acquired to confirm the required
428 chemical composition of all materials using a silicon drift detector (SDD) (Oxford Instruments
429 XMax 80, United Kingdom). The measurements were carried out under the next conditions:
430 accelerating voltage – 20 kV; beam intensity – 12; energy range – 20 keV. With the AZtecEnergy
431 software, the EDS maps were recalculated to quant maps. For raw materials, the samples were
432 placed directly on carbon tape. For Pt NPs onto a 2D material, sample preparation was carried out
433 by drop casting the suspension (3 mg/mL in isopropyl alcohol (IPA) on a TEM grid – Cu; 200
434 mesh; Formvar/carbon) followed by drying at room temperature.

435 Raman spectroscopy was used to provide structural characterization of sheets deposited with Pt
436 NPs and to understand the bonding between the NPs and support. Raman measurements were
437 carried out on an inVia Raman microscope (Renishaw, England) in backscattering geometry with
438 a CCD detector. The green line of a diode-pumped solid-state (DPSS) laser (532 nm, 50 mW) was
439 used as the excitation source. The Raman bands were collected with the applied power of 5 mW
440 and 100× magnification objective in the wavelength range of 200-3000 cm^{-1} and the grating of
441 2400 1/mm at room temperature. For instrument calibration, a peak position at 520 cm^{-1} was
442 achieved on a silicon reference with a resolution less than 1 cm^{-1} . The samples were suspended in
443 IPA (3 mg/mL), deposited on an ITO glass, and dried at room temperature. To characterize the
444 specific 2D sheet with Pt NPs, the triangulation app was used. Raman maps were collected with a
445 pixel size of $1.5 \times 1.5 \mu\text{m}$ and processed using self-written code.

446 TEM and selected area electron diffraction (SAED) were performed for the characterization of
447 pristine 2D materials and Pt NPs deposited onto a 2D material using an EFTEM Jeol 2200 FS
448 microscope (Jeol, Japan) at an acceleration voltage of 200 keV. For the preparation of pristine
449 material, the drop of the 2D material suspension (3 mg/mL in IPA) was deposited on a TEM grid
450 and allowed to dry at room temperature (“drop casting”). For the characterization of Pt NPs
451 deposited onto 2D materials, a regular square lattice pattern of NPs was deposited on all 2D
452 materials by EBL using the GIS system incorporated in the dual-beam FIB-SEM microscope.

453

454 **Supporting Information**

455 Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author

456

457 **Acknowledgements**

458 This project was supported by the Czech Science Foundation (GACR No. 23-08083M) and the
459 grant of Specific university research – grant No A2_FCHT_2024_056 at University of Chemistry
460 and Technology in Prague. The authors acknowledge the assistance provided by the Advanced
461 Multiscale Materials for Key Enabling Technologies project, supported by the Ministry of
462 Education, Youth, and Sports of the Czech Republic. Project No.
463 CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004558, Co-funded by the European Union. This project has received
464 funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant
465 agreement ID 101135196. Z.S. was supported by ERC-CZ program (project LL2101) from
466 Ministry of Education Youth and Sports (MEYS).

467

468 **Conflict of Interest**

469 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

470

471 **Data availability Statement**

472 Data Availability Statement: The datasets generated during and/or analyzed during the study are
473 accessible via the Zenodo repository: <https://zenodo.org/records/14175428>

474

475 **References**

- 476 [1] H. Feng, Y. Liu, J. Li, *Chemical Communications*. **2015**. *51*, 2418-2420.
- 477 [2] Y. Li, Y. Li, E. Zhu, T. McLouth, C.-Y. Chiu, X. Huang, Y. Huang, *Journal of the American*
478 *Chemical Society*. **2012**. *134*, 12326-12329.
- 479 [3] C. Xu, X. Wang, J. Zhu, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*. **2008**. *112*, 19841-19845.
- 480 [4] Y. Lin, Y. Pan, J. Zhang, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*. **2017**. *42*, 7951-7956.
- 481 [5] Y. Zhang, Q. Jiang, P. Lang, N. Yuan, J. Tang, *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*. **2021**.
482 *850*, 156580.
- 483 [6] X. Zhang, X. Zhao, D. Wu, Y. Jing, Z. Zhou, *Advanced science*. **2016**. *3*, 1600062.
- 484 [7] D.A. Kuznetsov, Z. Chen, P.V. Kumar, A. Tsoukalou, A. Kierzkowska, P.M. Abdala, O.V.
485 Safonova, A. Fedorov, C.R. Müller, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*. **2019**. *141*,
486 17809-17816.
- 487 [8] J. Wang, C. Liu, *ChemBioEng Reviews*. **2015**. *2*, 335-350.
- 488 [9] M. Yoo, E. Kang, H. Choi, H. Ha, H. Choi, J.-S. Choi, K.-S. Lee, R. Celestre, D.A. Shapiro,
489 J.Y. Park, *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*. **2022**. *10*, 5942-5952.
- 490 [10] P. Saikia, A.T. Miah, B. Malakar, A. Bordoloi, *Indian Journal of Materials Science*. **2015**.
491 *2015*, 658346.
- 492 [11] J. Ni, S. Shi, C. Zhang, B. Fang, X. Wang, J. Lin, S. Liang, B. Lin, L. Jiang, *Journal of*
493 *Catalysis*. **2022**. *409*, 78-86.
- 494 [12] T.K. Slot, F. Yue, H. Xu, E.V. Ramos-Fernandez, A. Sepúlveda-Escribano, Z. Sofer, G.
495 Rothenberg, N.R. Shiju, *2D Materials*. **2020**. *8*, 015001.
- 496 [13] N.S. Ahmed, R. Menzel, Y. Wang, A. Garcia-Gallastegui, S.M. Bawaked, A.Y. Obaid, S.N.
497 Basahel, M. Mokhtar, *Journal of Solid State Chemistry*. **2017**. *246*, 130-137.
- 498 [14] H. Gao, C. Zhai, H. Zhang, N. Fu, Y. Du, M. Zhu, *Energy Technology*. **2019**. *7*, 1900253.

- 499 [15] S.M. George, *Chemical reviews*. **2010**. *110*, 111-131.
- 500 [16] S. Lee, Y. Kang, J. Lee, J. Kim, J.W. Shin, S. Sim, D. Go, E. Jo, S. Kye, J. Kim, *Applied*
501 *Surface Science*. **2022**. *571*, 151256.
- 502 [17] A. Mackus, N. Thissen, J. Mulders, P. Trompenaars, M. Verheijen, A. Bol, W. Kessels, *The*
503 *Journal of Physical Chemistry C*. **2013**. *117*, 10788-10798.
- 504 [18] M. Altissimo, *Biomicrofluidics*. **2010**. *4*, 026503.
- 505 [19] C. Hagen, *Applied Physics A*. **2014**. *117*, 1599-1605.
- 506 [20] M. Huth, F. Porrati, C. Schwalb, M. Winhold, R. Sachser, M. Dukic, J. Adams, G. Fantner,
507 *Beilstein journal of nanotechnology*. **2012**. *3*, 597-619.
- 508 [21] M. Vesely, P. Marvan, J. Trejbal, V. Mazanek, J. Luxa, J. Sturala, Z. Sofer, *ACS applied*
509 *materials & interfaces*. **2020**. *12*, 22702-22709.
- 510 [22] W.S. Hummers Jr, R.E. Offeman, *Journal of the american chemical society*. **1958**. *80*,
511 1339-1339.
- 512 [23] D.C. Marcano, D.V. Kosynkin, J.M. Berlin, A. Sinitskii, Z. Sun, A. Slesarev, L.B.
513 Alemany, W. Lu, J.M. Tour, *ACS nano*. **2010**. *4*, 4806-4814.
- 514 [24] V. Scardaci, G. Compagnini, *C*. **2021**. *7*, 48.
- 515 [25] K.N. Kudin, B. Ozbas, H.C. Schniepp, R.K. Prud'Homme, I.A. Aksay, R. Car, *Nano letters*.
516 **2008**. *8*, 36-41.
- 517 [26] A. Hasani, H. Sharifi Dehsari, A. Amiri Zarandi, A. Salehi, F.A. Taromi, H. Kazeroni,
518 *Journal of Nanomaterials*. **2015**. *2015*.
- 519 [27] M. Thakran, S. Kumar, R. Phogat, S. Ray, R. Brajpuriya, A.S. Rana, B. Kumar, *J. Nano-*
520 *Electron. Phys*. **2021**. *13*, 10.21272.
- 521 [28] A. Castellanos-Gomez, L. Vicarelli, E. Prada, J.O. Island, K. Narasimha-Acharya, S.I.
522 Blanter, D.J. Groenendijk, M. Buscema, G.A. Steele, J. Alvarez, *2D Materials*. **2014**. *1*,
523 025001.
- 524 [29] H. Huang, Q. Xiao, J. Wang, X.-F. Yu, H. Wang, H. Zhang, P.K. Chu, *npj 2D Materials*
525 *and Applications*. **2017**. *1*, 20.
- 526 [30] I. Janowska, M.-S. Moldovan, O. Ersen, H. Bulou, K. Chizari, M.J. Ledoux, C. Pham-Huu,
527 *Nano Research*. **2011**. *4*, 511-521.
- 528 [31] A. Mahgoub, H. Lu, R.M. Thorman, K. Preradovic, L. McElwee-White, H. Fairbrother,
529 C.W. Hagen, *Beilstein journal of nanotechnology*. **2020**. *11*, 1789-1800.

- 530 [32] F. Schmidt, P. Swiderek, J.H. Bredehöft, *ACS Earth and Space Chemistry*. **2019**. 3, 1974-
531 1986.
- 532 [33] S. Stankovich, D.A. Dikin, R.D. Piner, K.A. Kohlhaas, A. Kleinhammes, Y. Jia, Y. Wu,
533 S.T. Nguyen, R.S. Ruoff, *Carbon*. **2007**. 45, 1558-1565.
- 534 [34] W. Lu, H. Nan, J. Hong, Y. Chen, C. Zhu, Z. Liang, X. Ma, Z. Ni, C. Jin, Z. Zhang, *Nano*
535 *Research*. **2014**. 7, 853-859.
- 536 [35] A. Molina-Sanchez, L. Wirtz, *Physical Review B*. **2011**. 84, 155413.
- 537 [36] C. Lee, H. Yan, L.E. Brus, T.F. Heinz, J. Hone, S. Ryu, *ACS nano*. **2010**. 4, 2695-2700.
- 538 [37] R. Krishna, J. Wade, A.N. Jones, M. Lasithiotakis, P.M. Mummery, B.J. Marsden, *Carbon*.
539 **2017**. 124, 314-333.
- 540 [38] R. Muzyka, S. Drewniak, T. Pustelny, M. Chrubasik, G. Gryglewicz, *Materials*. **2018**. 11,
541 1050.
- 542

543 I. Danylo, L. Koláčný, K. Kissíková, T. Hartman, M. Pitínová, J. Šturala, Z. Sofer*, M. Veselý*

544
545 **Direct Chemical Lithography Writing on 2D Materials by Electron Beam Induced Chemical**
546 **Reactions**

547
548 Direct electron beam lithography is studied for targeted platinum nanoparticle deposition onto 2D
549 supports: functionalized graphene oxide and black phosphorus. Depending on the 2D support,
550 Raman spectroscopy discloses a strong bond between the nanoparticles and the 2D sheets, which
551 allows an evaluation of the unique influence of nanoparticle-support interactions on enhanced
552 catalytic activity.

553

554